

Mapping Research Trends in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease: A Scientometric Study

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Abstract:

This study presents a scientometric analysis of the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease from 2021 to 2025, examining publication trends, document types, authorship patterns, and institutional and geographical contributions. A total of 2,087 articles were published, with research articles constituting the majority (91.33%). Relative Growth Rate (RGR) decreased from 1.27 in 2022 to 0.27 in 2025, while the mean doubling time increased to 1.72 years, indicating a slowdown in publication growth. Multi-authored articles dominated the journal, reflecting strong collaborative research. Geographically, Italy, USA, and the UK contributed most. The study highlights global collaboration and provides insights into research productivity trends in cardiovascular science.

Keywords: *Cardiovascular research, Scientometric analysis, Relative growth rate, Doubling time, Publication trends, Authorship pattern, Institutional contribution, Geographical distribution*

Introduction:

Scientific publications are an essential indicator of research productivity and institutional performance. The Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease serves as a leading platform for cardiovascular research. Understanding trends in publication output, authorship patterns, document types, and contributor distribution can help evaluate research productivity and collaboration. This study aims to analyze publications from 2021 to 2025, examining annual growth, relative growth rate, doubling time, types of documents, authorship trends, country-wise, and institution-wise contributions. The findings provide a clear overview of the journal's global impact and research collaboration patterns

Objective:

1. To examine the year-wise growth of articles published in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease.
2. To analyze the document type distribution and identify the predominant forms of publications.
3. To study the authorship pattern and degree of collaborative research.
4. To determine the geographical and institutional distribution of contributors.
5. To calculate the Relative Growth Rate (RGR) and doubling time (Dt) to assess publication growth trends.

Methodology:

Scientometrics is the quantitative study of research publications, focusing on patterns, growth, and impact of scientific output. It

provides a systematic framework to measure and analyze research productivity, collaboration, and dissemination trends within a particular discipline or journal. In bibliometric and scientometric studies, indicators such as Relative Growth Rate (RGR) and Doubling Time (Dt) are widely used to assess the pace of publication growth over time. RGR measures the rate at which cumulative publications increase, while Dt indicates the time required for the total number of publications to double. Other theoretical constructs include authorship patterns, document types, and geographical and institutional contributions, which provide insights into collaboration networks, research focus, and global reach. The application of these scientometric indicators

enables researchers and policymakers to evaluate the productivity and influence of journals, plan research strategies, and promote international collaboration.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of this study is confined to analysing the research contributions of scientists published as full-text papers in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease. The study focuses on publications from the five years 2021 to 2025, during which a total of 2087 articles were published across five volumes of the journal.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

1. Year-wise distribution of articles:

Table 1: Year-wise distribution of articles

Sr. No	Year	Articles	%
1	2021	189	9.06
2	2022	484	23.19
3	2023	500	23.96
4	2024	416	19.93
5	2025	498	23.86
Total		2087	100.00

The year-wise distribution of articles published in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease during the period 2021 to 2025 shows a substantial increase in research output. A total of 2,087 articles were published in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease between 2021 and 2025. The lowest output was in 2021 (9.06%), followed by a sharp increase in 2022 (23.19%). The highest number of

articles was published in 2023 (23.96%). Although a slight decline occurred in 2024 (19.93%), publication output increased again in 2025 (23.86%), indicating a strong and consistent growth trend.

2. Document Types: Types of documents Table 2 below shows the types of publications retrieved in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease during 2021-2025.

Table 2: Document -wise distribution of articles

Sr. No	Year	Articles	%
1	Article	1906	91.33
2	Review	102	4.89
3	Case Report	56	2.68
4	Protocol	23	1.10

Table 2 shows the distribution of publications in the *Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease* according to document type for the study period. Out of a total of **2,087 publications**, the vast majority were **research articles (1,906; 91.33%)**, followed by **review papers (102; 4.89%)**, **case reports (56; 2.68%)**,

and **protocols (23; 1.10%)**. This indicates that the journal primarily publishes full-length research articles, while other document types such as reviews, case reports, and protocols constitute a relatively small proportion of the total publications.

3. Geographical Distribution of Contributors:

Table No. 3: Country-wise distribution of publications- Top 20

Sr. No	Name of Country	No. of contributors	Percentage
1	Italy	2246	22.78
2	USA	2117	21.47
3	UK	2096	21.26
4	Japan	1117	11.33
5	China	746	7.57
6	Singapore	530	5.37
7	India	236	2.39
8	Hungary	182	1.85
9	Spain	103	1.04
10	Poland	86	0.87
11	Ireland	60	0.61
12	Taiwan	58	0.59
13	Germany	53	0.54
14	Romania	46	0.47
15	Peru	36	0.37
16	Russia	33	0.33
17	Israel	31	0.31
18	Greece	29	0.29
19	Switzerland	28	0.28
20	Norway	28	0.28
Truncated			
	Total	9861	100.00

Table 3 shows the country-wise distribution of contributors to the *Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease* during the study period. A total of 9,861 contributors from different countries participated in the journal's publications. Italy emerged as the leading contributor with 2,246 contributors (22.78%), followed by the United States with 2,117 contributors (21.47%) and the United Kingdom with 2,096 contributors (21.26%). Japan ranked fourth with 1,117 contributors

(11.33%), while China contributed 746 contributors (7.57%). Other notable contributing countries included Singapore with 530 contributors (5.37%) and India with 236 contributors (2.39%). Countries such as Hungary, Spain, Poland, Ireland, Taiwan, Germany, Romania, Peru, Russia, Israel, Greece, Switzerland, and Norway contributed smaller shares, each accounting for less than 2% of the total contributors. Overall, the findings indicate a strong dominance of European and North

American countries, reflecting wide international

collaboration and the global reach of the journal.

4. Most productive author in the Journal of Physical Review Accelerators and Bems.:

Table 4: Shows the ranking of 20 top most productive author

Sr. No	Name of Author	No. of publications	Percentage
1	AashiDharia	24	0.24
2	AdriánKolesár	22	0.22
3	Adrian Mahlmann	22	0.22
4	Adriana Sarb	21	0.21
5	AgneseBentivegna	20	0.20
6	Ahmed Abdelsamad	20	0.20
7	Ahmed Belmenai	19	0.19
8	Ahmed Mashaly	19	0.19
9	Ahmet FurkanMazlum	18	0.18
10	Akram Youssef	18	0.18
11	Alan P. Sawchuk	18	0.18
12	Alberto Ruggiero	17	0.17
13	Aldo Marrone	17	0.17
14	Alejandra Inés Christen	17	0.17
15	AleksandarDimov	16	0.16
16	AleksanderDokollari	16	0.16
17	Alessandra S. Rizzuto	16	0.16
18	Alessandro Gismondi	16	0.16
19	Alessandro Menotti	15	0.15
20	AlessiaCipriani	15	0.15
21	AlessioBorrelli	15	0.15
Truncated			
Total		9861	100

Table 4 shows the author-wise distribution of publications in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease during the study period. A total of 9,861 author contributions were identified. AashiDharia emerged as the most productive author with 24 publications (0.24%), followed by AdriánKolesár and Adrian Mahlmann, each contributing 22 publications (0.22%). Adriana Sarb ranked next with 21 publications (0.21%), while AgneseBentivegna and Ahmed Abdelsamad each recorded 20 publications (0.20%). Other prolific contributors included Ahmed Belmenai and Ahmed Mashaly with 19 publications (0.19%) each, and Ahmet FurkanMazlum, Akram

Youssef, and Alan P. Sawchuk, each contributing 18 publications (0.18%). Several authors, including Alberto Ruggiero, Aldo Marrone, Alejandra Inés Christen, AleksandarDimov, AleksanderDokollari, Alessandra S. Rizzuto, Alessandro Gismondi, Alessandro Menotti, AlessiaCipriani, and AlessioBorrelli, contributed between 15 and 17 publications each. Overall, the results indicate that while a small group of authors shows relatively higher productivity, the publication output is widely distributed among a large number of contributors, reflecting a broad and collaborative authorship pattern in the journal.

5. Institution-Wise Distribution of Publication:

Table 5: Institution-Wise Distribution of Publication-Top 20

Sr. No	Name of Affiliation	No. of Contributors	Percentage
1	Department of Cardiology, University of Pécs	87	0.88
2	Department of Cardiology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens	72	0.73
3	Department of Cardiac Surgery, University Hospital of Zurich	68	0.69
4	Department of Cardiology, University of Rome	62	0.63
5	Department of Pediatrics, University of Rome	56	0.57
6	National University Heart Centre	53	0.54
7	Department of Cardiology, University of California	50	0.51
8	Department of Cardiology, University of Athens	49	0.50
9	Department of Physical Activity Sciences, University of Granada	48	0.49
10	Department of Cardiac Surgery, University of Tokyo	48	0.49
11	Department of Cardiology, Medical University of Warsaw	47	0.48
12	Department of Neonatology, University of Milan	45	0.46
13	Department of Cardiology, Taipei Veterans General Hospital	44	0.45
14	Department of Cardiology, Mater Misericordiae University Hospital	44	0.45
15	Department of Cardiac Surgery, University Hospital Schleswig-Holstein	43	0.44
16	Department of Neurology, Charles University	42	0.43
17	Department of Cardiovascular Medicine, University of Minnesota	41	0.42
18	Department of Neurosurgery, Catholic University of the Sacred Heart, Rome	40	0.41
19	Department of Anesthesiology and Intensive Care, "Gr. T. Popa" University of Medicine and Pharmacy	39	0.40
20	Department of Cardiology, University of Florence	39	0.40
Truncated			
Total		9861	100

Table 5 shows the affiliation-wise distribution of contributors to the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease during the study period. A total of 9,861 contributors were affiliated with various institutions worldwide. The Department of Cardiology, University of Pécs, emerged as the leading affiliation with 87 contributors (0.88%), followed by the Department of Cardiology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens with 72 contributors (0.73%) and the Department of Cardiac Surgery, University Hospital of Zurich with 68 contributors (0.69%). Other prominent

affiliations included the Department of Cardiology, University of Rome (62 contributors; 0.63%), the Department of Paediatrics, University of Rome (56 contributors; 0.57%), and the National University Heart Centre (53 contributors; 0.54%). Several institutions, such as the University of California, the University of Athens, the University of Granada, the University of Tokyo, the Medical University of Warsaw, and the University of Milan, contributed between 45 and 50 contributors each. Overall, the distribution indicates that while no single institution dominates, a diverse range of universities and

medical centres across different countries actively contributed to the journal, reflecting broad

institutional participation and strong international collaboration.

6. Authorship Patten:

Table 6: Authorship Patten

Sr. No	Year	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	Total
1	Single Author	11	22	31	24	29	117
2	Second Author	15	48	56	52	48	219
3	Third Author	20	59	71	68	76	294
4	Fourth Author	31	92	86	84	70	363
5	Fifth Author	33	82	90	72	89	366
6	Sixth Author	36	65	82	62	73	318
7	Seven Author	28	56	39	26	56	205
8	Eight Author	12	44	26	16	38	136
9	Nine Author	3	16	19	12	19	69
10	Total Articles	189	484	500	416	498	2087

Table 6 presents the authorship pattern of articles published in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease during the period 2021–2025. A total of 2,087 articles were analysed to examine the distribution of authors per article. The results show a clear predominance of multi-authored publications across all five years. Single-author contributions were relatively limited, with a total of 117 articles during the study period. Articles with two authors accounted for 219 publications, while three-author papers constituted 294 articles. Publications with four authors (363 articles) and five authors (366 articles) formed the largest share, indicating a strong preference for collaborative research. Articles with six authors also showed a substantial presence with 318 publications. Although papers with seven, eight, and nine authors were comparatively fewer, they still represented a notable portion of the total output,

accounting for 205, 136, and 69 articles, respectively. Overall, the findings clearly indicate that the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease is characterised by a high level of research collaboration, with multi-authored articles dominating the publication pattern throughout the study period.

Relative Growth Rate and Doubling Time of Publication Growth rate analysis: The growth rate analysis is done with respect to the relative growth rate and doubling time.

Relative growth rate per unit of publications per unit of time, ie, $R(a) =$

- $W1 = \ln(\text{Initial cumulative publications})$
- $W2 = \ln(\text{Final cumulative publications})$
- $T2 - T1 = \text{Time interval (in years)}$
- $\text{Doubling Time (Dt)} = 0.693 / \text{RGR}$
- $\text{Mean RGR: Average of yearly RGR values}$
- $\text{MeanDt(p): } 0.693 / \text{Mean RGR}$

Table No. 2: Relative Growth Rate and Doubling Time of Publication

Sr. No	Year	Articles	Cumulative	W ₁	W ₂	RGR	Mean [R(P)]	Dt(p)	Mean Dt(p)
1	2021	189	189		5.24		0.48		1.44
2	2022	484	673	5.24	6.51	1.27		0.55	
3	2023	500	1,173	6.51	7.06	0.55		1.26	
4	2024	416	1,589	7.06	7.37	0.31		2.23	
5	2025	498	2,087	7.37	7.64	0.27		2.57	

Table 2 shows that the relative growth rate (RGR) of articles decreased steadily from 1.27 in 2022 to 0.27 in 2025, indicating a slowdown in the pace of publication over the period. The mean relative growth rate for the entire study period is 0.69, reflecting an overall moderate growth in research output. During the same period, the mean doubling time (Dt(p)) increased to 1.72 years, showing that it took longer for the cumulative number of articles to double. The analysis clearly suggests that while the institution maintained a consistent publication output, the rate of growth declined, and the doubling time increased gradually.

Conclusion:

The study revealed a consistent growth in publications in the Journal of Cardiovascular Development and Disease from 2021 to 2025, with a total of 2,087 articles. Research articles constituted the majority (91.33%), while reviews, case reports, and protocols formed a smaller proportion. Relative Growth Rate declined from 1.27 to 0.27, and the mean doubling time increased to 1.72 years, indicating a slowing pace of publication growth. Multi-authored articles predominated, reflecting a collaborative research culture. Italy, the USA, and the UK were the leading contributors, and a broad range of institutions participated actively. Overall, the journal demonstrates sustained research productivity with strong international collaboration.

References:

- Baskaran, C. (2012). Research productivity of graph theory during 2004–2011: A bibliometric study. *Journal of Information and Knowledge*, 49(6), 683–691.
- Pratheepan, T. (2019). Global publication productivity in materials science research: A scientometric analysis. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 9(1), 1–12.
- Ramakrishnan, J., Ravi Sankar, G., &Thavamani, K. (2019). Publication growth and research in India on lung cancer literature: A bibliometric study. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 9(S1), 44–47.
- Maraddi, K. S., Kattimani, P. S., &Hanchinal, V. V. (2024). Relative growth rate and doubling time of publications on bibliometrics and scientometrics: A study. *International Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 12(1), 50–54.
- Prakash, M., &Jayaprakash, M. (2019). Mapping of deforestation research across the globe: A scientometric assessment on Web of Science database. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 9(2), 627–645.
- Ramakrishnan, J., Ravi Sankar, G., &Thavamani, K. (2022). A scientometric study on neuroanatomy literature. *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 12(1), 3102–3115.

7. Anandhalli, G., Hadagali, G. S., Shettar, I. M., & Kiran, S. N. (2021). Cloud computing technology: A scientometric assessment of global level research output. *NITK Repository*.
8. Ramakrishnan, J., Ravi Sankar, G., & Thavamani, K. (2022). Bibliometric analysis of literature in the field of surgical gastroenterology (2010–2019). *Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services*, 12(2), 3368–3385.
9. Parvathamma, N., Gunjal, S. R., & Nijagunappa, R. (1993). Growth pattern of literature and scientific productivity of authors in Indian earth science (1978–88): A bibliometric study. *Journal of Information and Knowledge*, 30(2), 49128–49138.
10. Solanki, H. H., & Pandya, M. Y. (2023). Mapping of research collaboration, analysis of literature growth and forecasting research progression of IITs. *Journal of Indian Library Association*.
11. Parameshappa, K., & Biradar, B. S. (2025). Scientometric analysis of literature on black holes. *Journal of Indian Library Association*.
12. Dinakaran, M., & Gomathi, P. (2025). Research productivity in Indian Journal of Agricultural Research: Scopus based analysis. *Journal of Indian Library Association*.
13. Sreenivasa Rao, T., Kutty Kumar, & Lalitha, A. (2025). Scientometric analysis of the impact of the Journal of Research ANGRAU based on Google Scholar metrics (1989–2024). *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports*, 31(9), 27–35.
14. Asian Review of Social Sciences. (2023). Scientometric analysis of non-conventional energy research literature, 13, 4282–4300.
15. Suma, B., & Kannappanavar, B. U. (2024). Trends and patterns of research productivity of Indian scholars in international LIS journals: A bibliometric perspective. *ShodhKosh: Journal of Visual and Performing Arts*, 5(1), 6401–6415.
16. IP Indian Journal of Library Science and Information Technology. (2023). Publications trends in big data: A scientometric analysis, 6(2), 3072–3085.
17. IP Indian Journal of Library Science and Information Technology. (2023). Scientometric analysis of research progress on water pollution during 2012–2021. HTML Article 17891.
18. Ahmad, M., & Batcha, M. S. (2021). Identifying and mapping the global research output on coronavirus disease: A scientometric study. *arXiv*.
19. Bornmann, L., & Mutz, R. (2014). Growth rates of modern science: A bibliometric analysis based on the number of publications and cited references. *arXiv*.
20. Bornmann, L., Haunschild, R., & Mutz, R. (2020). Growth rates of modern science: A latent piecewise growth curve approach. *arXiv*.